

Uncovering the Key Role of Distortion in Bioorthogonal Tetrazine Tools that Defy the Reactivity/Stability Tradeoff

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1) Computational methods and results

Theoretical calculations were performed using the software package Gaussian16 RevC.01.^[1] Geometry optimizations and frequency analyses were performed using the ω B97X-D density functional^[2] and the 6-311G(d,p) basis set in 1,4-dioxane using the SMD^[3] model. A quasi-harmonic correction to entropy was applied by setting all frequencies below 100 cm⁻¹ to 100 cm⁻¹ using GoodVibes.^[4] All possible conformers were considered. Single imaginary frequencies corresponding to the desired reaction coordinates were obtained only in the case of transition state (TS) calculations. No imaginary frequencies were obtained for all other structures. Orbital energies were calculated at the HF/6-311+G(d,p)-SMD(1,4-dioxane)// ω B97X-D/6-311G(d,p)-SMD(1,4-dioxane) level of theory. Distortion/interaction analyses were performed using autoDIAS.^[5] The calculated energies are summarized in Table S1. Coordinates of all optimized geometries are provided as *.xyz files.

Table S1. ω B97X-D/6-311G(d,p)-SMD(1,4-dioxane) calculated energies for all investigated Tz and the transition states for the reactions with TCO and ethylene.

Structure	ΔE (hartree)	ZPE (hartree)	ΔH_{298} (hartree)	ΔG_{298} (hartree)
TCO	-313.232583	0.204800	-313.019344	-313.058930
Ph	-527.320368	0.133779	-527.177034	-527.220506
2Pyr	-543.349967	0.121652	-543.218841	-543.262222
3Pyr	-543.352935	0.121878	-543.221578	-543.264956
4Pyr	-543.352053	0.121656	-543.220910	-543.264345
MVE	-412.997911	0.113361	-412.875847	-488.112664
MV	-412.997911	0.113361	-412.875847	-412.916845
TS_{Ph_TCO}	-840.550682	0.340848	-840.192584	-840.251534
TS_{2Pyr_TCO}	-856.584023	0.328994	-856.237907	-856.296723
TS_{3Pyr_TCO}	-856.583923	0.329152	-856.237621	-856.296451
TS_{4Pyr_TCO}	-856.584047	0.329015	-856.237860	-856.296762
TS_{MVE_TCO}	-801.430038	0.325624	-801.087097	-801.146087
TS_{MV_TCO}	-726.227561	0.320584	-725.890618	-725.947504
ethylene	-78.580105	0.051159	-78.524966	-78.551118
TS_{Ph_ethylene}	-605.881285	0.188576	-605.681211	-605.728542
TS_{2Pyr_ethylene}	-621.914597	0.176552	-621.726632	-621.773951
TS_{3Pyr_ethylene}	-621.914324	0.176797	-621.726137	-621.773359
TS_{4Pyr_ethylene}	-621.914469	0.176605	-621.726439	-621.773758

Figure S1. (a) Calculated Kohn-Sham LUMO+1 energies (ω B97X-D/6-311G(d,p)-SMD(1,4-dioxane)); (b) Measured rate constants vs. calculated Kohn-Sham LUMO+1 energy (cf. HF orbital energies in Fig. 2c); (c) Stability of Tz in cell growth medium at 37 °C ($n = 3$, SD < 5%) vs. Kohn-Sham LUMO+1 energy (cf. HF orbital energies in Fig. 5b).

Figure S2. Calculated free energies of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) vs. the natural logarithm of the observed second order rate constants (k) for the IEDDA reactions of Ph, 2Pyr, 3Pyr, and 4Pyr with TCO^[6].

Figure S3. Dihedral angle in the TS for the reaction of Ph, 2Pyr, 3Pyr, and 4Pyr with (a) TCO and (b) ethylene.

Distortion/interaction analysis at consistent geometry

Different asynchronicity at the transition state can lead to skewed results in a distortion/interaction analysis. To verify the results as shown in Fig. 3b we performed the analysis using a consistent length of forming bonds for the IEDDA reaction of **Ph**, **2Pyr**, **3Pyr**, and **4Pyr** with **TCO**. At the transition state **2Pyr** shows a slightly more synchronous transition state with one bond being 0.03 to 0.04 Å longer and the other bond being 0.02 to 0.03 Å shorter than for the other tetrazines. Even at the transition state all bond lengths are within 0.04 Å. For the consistent geometry the bond lengths were set to 2.15 Å and 2.32 Å, respectively. Table S2 summarizes the results of the distortion/interaction analysis at the transition state and at the selected consistent geometry. While the calculated values vary slightly, the observed trends are very similar in both cases. In particular, the calculated distortion energy (ΔE_{dist}) for **2Pyr** is considerably lower than the value obtained for **4Pyr**, indicating the key role of ΔE_{dist} regarding the high reactivity of 2-pyridyl-substituted tetrazines.

Table S2. Distortion/interaction analysis at the transition state and consistent geometry.

Tz	Transition state			Consistent geometry		
	ΔE (kcal/mol)	ΔE_{dist} (kcal/mol)	ΔE_{int} (kcal/mol)	ΔE (kcal/mol)	ΔE_{dist} (kcal/mol)	ΔE_{int} (kcal/mol)
Ph	1.8	18.8	-17.0	1.8	18.2	-16.5
2Pyr	-1.0	17.1	-18.1	-0.9	17.9	-18.9
3Pyr	1.4	18.7	-17.3	1.4	18.6	-17.2
4Pyr	0.8	18.5	-17.8	0.8	19.0	-18.3

NBO analysis

To further investigate the interaction between **2Pyr** and **TCO** at the transition state, an interaction analysis using NBO 6.0^[7] was performed, identifying two additional interactions that are enabled by the rotation of the pyridyl group: (1) a weak hydrogen bond between the pyridyl nitrogen lone pair and the vinylic CH bond of **TCO** with a second-order perturbation energy of 0.37 kcal mol⁻¹ (Fig. S4a); (2) an $n_{\text{N}} \rightarrow \sigma^*_{\text{C-N}}$ interaction between the pyridyl lone pair and one of the C-N bonds in the tetrazine, which is already present in the reactant (0.33 kcal mol⁻¹) and increases to 0.60 kcal mol⁻¹ in the transition state (Fig. S4b).

Figure S4. (a) NBO analysis of the intermolecular hydrogen bond at the transition state (**2Pyr+TCO**). (b) NBO analysis of the intramolecular $n_{\text{N}} \rightarrow \sigma^*_{\text{C-N}}$ interaction in the reactant (**2Pyr**, left) and the transition state (right). Bonding orbital shown in red/blue, antibonding in purple/teal.

2) Synthesis

General methods

Unless otherwise noted, reactions were carried out under an atmosphere of argon in air-dried glassware with magnetic stirring. Air- and/or moisture-sensitive liquids were transferred via syringe. All reagents were purchased from commercial sources without further purification. Dichloromethane (DCM) was dried using PURESOLV-columns (Inert Corporation, USA). Solvents used for flash column chromatography were purchased from Donau Chemie AG (Austria). Dry acetonitrile was commercially obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) and stored under argon. Column chromatography was performed using a BUCHI Sepacore Flash System (2 x BUCHI Pump Module C-605, BUCHI Pump Manager C-615, BUCHI UV Photometer C-635, and BUCHI Fraction Collector C-660) and a Reveleris® X2 Flash Chromatography/Prep Purification Systems (BUCHI). Silica gel 60 (40-63 μm) was obtained from Merck. A Kinetex® 5 μm C18 100 Å, AXIA LC column (100 x 30.0 mm, Phenomenex) was used for preparative HPLC. HPLC grade solvents were purchased from VWR (USA). ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC 200 MHz, Bruker Avance UltraShield 400 MHz or Bruker Ascend 600 MHz spectrometer at 20 °C. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm (δ) relative to tetramethylsilane and calibrated using solvent residual peaks. Data is shown as follows: Chemical shift, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, quint = quintet, m = multiplet, b = broad signal), coupling constants (J , Hz) and integration. HRMS analysis was carried out using methanol solutions (concentration: 10 ppm) on an Agilent 6230 LC TOFMS mass spectrometer equipped with an Agilent Dual AJS ESI-Source. The mass spectrometer was connected to a liquid chromatography system of the 1100/1200 series from Agilent Technologies (Palo Alto, CA, USA).

General procedure A for the synthesis of H-aryl-Tz

To a mixture of nitrile (1 eq.), sulfur (2 eq.), ethanol (15 eq.) and dichloromethane (1 eq.) in a microwave-vial was added hydrazine monohydrate (8 eq.) and the vial was sealed subsequently. The reaction mixture was stirred at 60 °C for the time specified after which it was cooled in an ice-bath and a solution of sodium nitrite (6.5 eq.) in water (10 mL) was added followed by addition of acetic acid (9 mL). The resulting colorful solution was extracted with DCM (4 x 100 mL), the combined organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered, and concentrated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography.

3-Phenyl-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (Ph)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure A using benzonitrile (200 mg, 1.94 mmol), sulfur (124.4 mg, 3.88 mmol), ethanol (1.7 mL, 29 mmol), dichloromethane (124 μL , 1.94 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (777 μL , 15.52 mmol) for 21 h. After oxidation, purification was performed by preparative column chromatography (Silica 100A, Phenomenex Luna 10u, 250 x 21.2 mm, 10 μm , 0-10% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to give the desired product as a pink solid (17 mg, 6%). Spectroscopic data matched that reported previously.^[8]

3-(2-Pyridyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (2Pyr)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure A using 2-pyridinecarbonitrile (200 mg, 1.92 mmol), sulfur (123.1 mg, 3.84 mmol), ethanol (1.7 mL, 29 mmol), dichloromethane (122 μL , 1.92 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (744 μL , 15.36 mmol) for 21 h. After oxidation, purification was performed by column chromatography (50-90% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to give the desired product as a pink solid (47 mg, 15%). Spectroscopic data matched that previously reported.^[9]

3-(3-Pyridyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (3Pyr)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure A using 3-pyridinecarbonitrile (200 mg, 1.92 mmol), sulfur (123.1 mg, 3.84 mmol), ethanol (1.7 mL, 29 mmol), dichloromethane (122 μ L, 1.92 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (744 μ L, 15.36 mmol) for 21 h. After oxidation, purification was performed by column chromatography (40-70% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to give the desired product as a pink solid (78 mg, 26%); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.32 (s, 1H), 9.83–9.86 (m, 1H), 8.99–8.92 (m, 2H), 7.60–7.56 (m, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 165.64, 158.41, 153.75, 149.64, 135.69, 127.86, 124.22; HRMS $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ m/z calcd. 160.0618 for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_5^+$, found 160.0615.

3-(4-Pyridyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (4Pyr)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure A using 4-pyridinecarbonitrile (200 mg, 1.92 mmol), sulfur (123.1 mg, 3.84 mmol), ethanol (1.7 mL, 29 mmol), dichloromethane (122 μ L, 1.92 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (744 μ L, 15.36 mmol) for 20 h. After oxidation, purification was performed by preparative column chromatography (Silica 100A, Phenomenex Luna 10u, 250 x 21.2 mm, 10 μ m, 20-40% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to afford the desired product as a pink solid (17 mg, 6%); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.36 (s, 1H), 8.95 (dd, $J = 6.1, 2.7$ Hz, 2H), 8.5 (dd, $J = 6.1, 2.8$ Hz, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 165.53, 158.76, 151.16, 139.33, 121.71; HRMS $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ m/z calcd. 160.0618 for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_5^+$, found 160.0615.

General procedure B for the synthesis of methyl-aryl-Tz

To a well-blended mixture of nitrile (1 eq.), acetonitrile (5-7 eq.) and catalytic amounts of NiCl_2 or $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ (0.25-0.3 eq.) was added hydrazine monohydrate (10-25 eq.). The reaction mixture was stirred at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 h after which it was cooled in an ice-bath and a solution of sodium nitrite (6.5 eq.) in water (10 mL) was added followed by the addition of acetic acid or aqueous 2N HCl. The resulting colorful solution was extracted with DCM (4 x 100 mL), the combined organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered, and concentrated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography.

3-Methyl-6-phenyl-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (MePh)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure B using benzonitrile (6 g, 58 mmol), acetonitrile (16.7 g, 408 mmol), NiCl_2 (0.3 g, 3 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (72 g, 1.5 mol). After oxidation, purification was performed by column chromatography (EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to give the desired product as a pink solid (420 mg, 4%). Spectroscopic data matched that previously reported.^[8]

3-Methyl-6-(2-pyridyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (Me2Pyr)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure B using 2-pyridinecarbonitrile (250 mg, 2.4 mmol), acetonitrile (627 μ L, 12 mmol), $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ (218 mg, 0.6 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (1.4 mL, 28.8 mmol). After oxidation, purification was performed by column chromatography (40-80% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to give the desired product as a pink solid (83 mg, 20%). Spectroscopic data matched that previously reported.^[10]

3-Methyl-6-(3-pyridyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (Me3Pyr)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure B using 3-pyridinecarbonitrile (500 mg, 4.8 mmol), acetonitrile (1.3 mL, 24 mmol), Zn(OTf)₂ (436 mg, 1.2 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (2.8 mL, 57.6 mmol). After oxidation, purification was performed by column chromatography (50-90% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to afford the desired product as a purple solid (37 mg, 4%). Spectroscopic data matched that previously reported.^[11]

3-Methyl-6-(4-pyridyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (Me4Pyr)

Synthesis was carried out according to general procedure B using 4-cyanopyridine (540 mg, 5.2 mmol), acetonitrile (1.1 mL, 26.8 mmol), Zn(OTf)₂ (473 mg, 1.3 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (2.5 g, 50 mmol). After oxidation, purification was performed by column chromatography (5%-40% EtOAc in hexanes, gradient elution) to afford the desired product as a purple solid (125 mg, 14%). Spectroscopic data matched that previously reported.^[11]

Synthesis of vinyl ether-substituted Tz

3-Methyl-6-(1-ethoxyvinyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (MeEVE)

Synthesis was performed similar to a known procedure.^[12] A mixture of 3-([1,1'-Biphenyl]-4-ylmethylthio)-6-methyl-1,2,4,5-tetrazine^[13] (75 mg, 0.25 mmol), tributyl(1-ethoxyvinyl)tin (172 μ L, 0.51 mmol), CuTc (97 mg, 0.51 mmol) and Pd(PPh)₃ (44 mg, 40 μ mol) in dry dioxane (51 mL) was stirred at 100 °C for 20 min. Purification by column chromatography (10% K₂CO₃ modified silica, 7-75% DCM in hexanes, gradient elution) gave the desired product as a pink solid (10.2 mg, 24%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) δ 5.87 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 4.86 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 4.08 (q, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 3.03 (s, 3H), 1.48 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 3H); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) δ 168.1, 162.3, 154.3, 92.7, 64.9, 21.4, 14.5.

Note: MeEVE was stored as 5 mM solution in CD₂Cl₂ in -20°C to prevent self-condensation.^[12]

3-Methyl-6-(3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-6-yl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (MeDHP)

Synthesis was performed analogously to MeEVE using 3-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-ylmethylthio)-6-methyl-1,2,4,5-tetrazine^[13] (75 mg, 0.25 mmol), tributyl(5,6-dihydro-4H-pyran-2-yl)stannane (170 μ L, 0.51 mmol), CuTc (97 mg, 0.51 mmol) and Pd(PPh)₃ (44 mg, 40 μ mol) in dry dioxane (51 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 26 min. Purification by preparative column chromatography (Silica 100 A, Phenomenex Luna 10u, 250 x 21.2 mm, 10 μ m, 0-1% DCM in MeOH) gave the desired product as a red oil (4.9 mg, 11%); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.69 (t, *J* = 4.2 Hz, 1H), 4.35 (t, *J* = 5.1 Hz, 2H), 3.05 (s, 3H), 2.39 (q, *J* = 4.6 Hz, 2H), 2.04 (quint, *J* = 5.3 Hz, 2H); ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 167.3, 161.2, 146.7, 110.3, 67.3, 21.9, 21.3, 21.2.

3,6-Bis(3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-6-yl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (DHP₂)

Synthesis was performed analogously to MeEVE using 3,6-bis(methylthio-1,2,4,5-tetrazine) (44 mg, 0.25 mmol), tributyl(5,6-dihydro-4H-pyran-2-yl)stannane (340 μ L, 1.0 mmol), CuTc (192 mg, 1.0 mmol) and Pd(PPh)₃ (44 mg, 40 μ mol) in dry dioxane (51 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 65 min. Purification by preparative column chromatography (Silica 100A, Phenomenex Luna 10u, 250 x 21.2 mm, 10 μ m, 0-20% DCM in MeOH, gradient elution) gave the desired product as red crystals (12.8 mg, 21%); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.71 (t, *J* = 4.3 Hz, 2H), 4.34 (t, *J* = 5.0 Hz, 4H), 2.39 (q, *J* = 4.7 Hz, 4H), 2.03 (quint, *J* = 5.1 Hz, 4H); ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 160.9, 146.8, 110.7, 67.2, 21.9, 21.3.

3) Reaction kinetics

Sample preparation

TCO^[6] was dissolved in dry 1,4-dioxane to reach a concentration of 2 mM.

An approx. 20 mM stock solution of TCO-PEG₄^[14] in DMSO was prepared. The exact concentration was determined by absorbance titration with DMT (extinction coefficient 510 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 520 nm), quantifying the decrease in tetrazine absorbance upon reaction with TCO. The initial DMSO stock was diluted with Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (DPBS) to prepare solutions for stopped-flow analysis at a final TCO concentration of 1 mM.

Tetrazines **Ph**, **2Pyr**, **3Pyr**, and **4Pyr** were dissolved in dry 1,4-dioxane to reach a concentration of approx. 10 μM and used for stopped-flow analysis.

20 mM stock solutions of compounds **MePh**, **Me2Pyr**, **Me3Pyr**, **Me4Pyr**, **2Pyr₂**, **MeEVE**, **MeDHP**, and **DHP₂** in DMSO were prepared. Serial dilution into DPBS gave solutions for stopped-flow analysis at a tetrazine concentration of 100 μM.

Stopped-flow spectrophotometry

Stopped-flow measurements were performed using an SX20-LED stopped-flow spectrophotometer (Applied Photophysics) equipped with a 535nm LED (optical pathlength 10 mm, full width half-maximum 34 nm) to monitor the characteristic tetrazine visible light absorbance (520-540 nm). The reagent syringes were loaded with tetrazine and TCO solutions and the instrument was primed. Measurements were done in sextuplicate for each tetrazine. Reactions were conducted at 25 °C or 37 °C and recorded automatically at the time of acquisition.

Data analysis

Data sets were analyzed by fitting an exponential decay using Prism 6 (Graphpad) to calculate the observed pseudo-first order rate constants that were converted into second order rate constants (Table S3) by dividing through the concentration of excess TCO used.

Table S3. Determined second order rate constants (n = 6, SD < 1%).

Tetrazine	Dienophile	Conditions	Second order rate constant (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Ph	TCO	1,4-dioxane, 25 °C	100
2Pyr	TCO	1,4-dioxane, 25 °C	620
3Pyr	TCO	1,4-dioxane, 25 °C	175
4Pyr	TCO	1,4-dioxane, 25 °C	387
MePh	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	990
Me2Pyr	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	5120
Me3Pyr	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	1180
Me4Pyr	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	2740
MeEVE	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	2750
MeDHP	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	1820
DHP ₂	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	6450
2Pyr ₂	TCO-PEG ₄	DPBS, 37 °C	69400

4) Stability and solubility of tetrazines

Analytical stock solutions and solvents

The stability of tetrazines was assessed in full cell growth medium (DMEM (fluorobrite) + 10% FBS). Therefore, 20 mM stock solutions of all tetrazines (**Me2Pyr**, **Me3Pyr**, **Me4Pyr**, **MeEVE**, **MeDHP**, **DHP₂**, **2Pyr₂**) in DMSO were prepared and further diluted into medium to reach a final concentration of 500 μM (DMSO content (v/v): 2.5%).

Stability measurements

All tetrazine solutions were incubated in absorption cuvettes (1 mL) in triplicates at 37 °C. After 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 h the tetrazine absorbance at 520 nm was measured on a Shimadzu UV1800 spectrophotometer with a temperature-controlled sample slide at 37 °C. After spectrometric analysis, incubation at 37 °C was continued and the procedure was repeated until the last measurement (24 h). The measured absorbance was compared to the absorbance at the initial value at 0 h to calculate the remaining fraction (%) of intact Tz (Table S4). At each time-point, freshly prepared Tz samples were measured to correct for variability of the measurement setup.

Table S4. Intact fraction of Tz (%) after incubation in DMEM + 10% FBS at 37 °C (n = 3, SD < 5%).

Time (h)	MePh	Me2Pyr	Me3Pyr	Me4Pyr	MeEVE	MeDHP	DHP ₂	2Pyr ₂
3	97	95	100	86	99	97	97	69
6	98	93	97	68	98	96	95	40
9	99	87	93	49	97	94	93	16
12	100	80	88	34	94	94	92	5
24	99	46	70	13	82	92	91	<1

In applications that require extended stability of the Tz (>10 h), **DHP₂** outperforms highly reactive **2Pyr₂**, even when using an excess of Tz (to compensate for degradation), as shown by the calculated apparent rate constants for the click reaction of pre-administered Tz (Fig. S5). In a similar analysis (taking into account stability and reactivity) the methyltetrazines **MePh**, **Me2Pyr**, **Me4Pyr**, **MeEVE**, and **MeDHP** have been compared (Fig. S6).

Figure S5. Calculation of apparent rate constants ($k_{r,i}$), taking into account the reactivity and stability of Tz.

Figure S6. (a) Stability of the methyltetrazines **MePh**, **Me2Pyr**, **Me4Pyr**, **MeEVE**, and **MeDHP** under physiological conditions (full cell growth medium, 37 °C, n = 3, SD < 5%), and (b) apparent rate constants ($k_{r,i}$).

Water solubility of tetrazines

To demonstrate the improved water solubility of vinyl ether-tetrazines, as indicated by data reported by Fox *et al.*,^[12] we have prepared solutions of **MeEVE**, **MeDHP**, and **DHP₂** in water at a concentration of 2 mM. In contrast, **MePh** and **2Pyr₂** were not completely soluble at this level (Fig. S7), as suggested by calculated LogP values (cLogP, Chemicalize, ChemAxon).

Figure S7. In contrast to **MePh** and **2Pyr₂**, the vinyl ether-tetrazines **MeEVE**, **MeDHP**, and **DHP₂** are completely soluble in water at a concentration of 2 mM.

5) NMR Spectra

Compound **3Pyr**, ^1H NMR

Compound **3Pyr**, ^{13}C NMR

Compound **4Pyr**, ^1H NMR

Compound **4Pyr**, ^{13}C NMR

Compound **MeEVE**, ^1H NMR

Compound **MeEVE**, ^{13}C NMR

Compound **MeDHP**, ^1H NMR

Compound **MeDHP**, ^{13}C NMR

Compound **DHP₂**, ¹H NMR

Compound **DHP₂**, ¹³C NMR

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